

CULTIVATE PROJECT - EIP AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

POLICY BRIEF ON BARCELONA FOOD SHARING GOVERNANCE

Food sharing is experiencing rapid growth in cities throughout Europe, presenting significant opportunities to promote sustainability and equity within urban food systems. The Food Sharing Governance Landscape Analysis in Barcelona seeks to **deepen the understanding of the governance landscape** surrounding various food sharing initiatives, including community gardens, food waste recovery and redistribution initiatives, and initiatives emerging from the social and solidarity economy. The evidence of this report is based on primary and secondary data, mainly relying on a combination of document analysis and interviews with key stakeholders to understand which critical elements shape the governance of food-sharing initiatives in Barcelona. The report examines the **regulatory frameworks that impact the initiatives** in these three areas, the key actors involved, their relations, and the diversity of the projects emerging in each of these three food sharing areas. Moreover, it identifies the primary beneficiaries of food sharing initiatives and characterises the **barriers and enablers** that affect their success. Ultimately, for each of these three areas, the report offers **recommendations** for local governments, food-sharing initiatives, and the private sector to foster their development and maximise the impact of these community efforts in terms of sustainability and equity.

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Barcelona's tradition of self-mobilization and solidarity bolsters food sharing initiatives.

To thrive, food sharing initiatives require stable funding and spaces, visibility, and enhanced collaboration to expand its impact.

Urban development and gentrification pose significant challenges, necessitating further regulation and support to secure spaces for these initiatives.

While political commitment exists to support food sharing initiatives, improving institutional coherence, coordination and implementation of regulation is essential.

Food sharing initiatives would benefit from a unified strategy by food sharing area.

Overall, food sharing initiatives hold great potential for transforming Barcelona's food system..

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

Food Sharing Governance Landscape Analysis in CULTIVATE hub locations: Barcelona: zenodo.org/records/12548970

L'agricultura urbana compartida a la ciutat de Barcelona: una anàlisi de governança: zenodo.org/records/11921944

Reaprofitament i redistribució alimentària: una anàlisi de governança: zenodo.org/records/14849499

Can Calopa in Barcelona.

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